

DEMOGRAPHIC RISK FACTORS FOR CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES

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Diabetes mellitus is a widespread, heterogeneous and chronic disease, which is life-threatening with its various complications due to insufficient glycemic control. Cardiovascular complications are the leading among these complications. It is important to determine the causes of the development of these complications and eliminate risk factors.

The purpose of the study. Identification of demographic risk factors for cardiovascular disease in patients with type 2 diabetes.

Inspection materials and methods. 711 patients over 30 years of age with type 2 diabetes were diagnosed, 54% of whom were women and 46% were men. The average age of men was 53.3 ± 1.02 years, and the average age of women was 60.3 ± 1.13 years. The duration of diabetes was 10.0 ± 1.21 years, the duration of cardiovascular diseases was 34% in men and 40% in women. Obesity was observed in 18% of men and 29% of women, and arterial hypertension was observed in 21% of men and 29% of women. In these patients, the family history of cardiovascular diseases was studied and analyzed.

Research results. 494 of 711 patients (69.6%) had a positive family history of hypertension, myocardial infarction, stroke, ischemic heart disease and heart failure. There was no reliable difference between women and men in the incidence of cardiovascular diseases (Fisher's exact test statistic is 0.5131). 30.4% of the patients' close relatives were not diagnosed with cardiovascular disease.

According to the history of myocardial infarction, it was observed in 11.5% of cases. This figure for stroke is 6.6%. The incidence of obesity corresponds to 38.2% of obesity of the 1st-2nd degree, and obesity of the 3rd degree was found in 1.2% of cases. 20% of men had a waist circumference of more than 102 cm, and 58% of women had a waist circumference of more than 88 cm. Arterial blood pressure from 160/100 to 179/109 mm.hg. up to 28.9% of patients' anamnesis, higher than 180/110 in 24.9% of cases.

Conclusion. Demographic risk factors of cardiovascular diseases were determined in patients with type 2 diabetes. Accordingly, measures to eliminate modifiable risk factors should be taken to reduce the occurrence of cardiovascular diseases in patients with type 2 diabetes. In addition, it is necessary to establish strict control of body mass index and waist circumference. The fact that arterial hypertension is in normotensive state only in 23% of patients indicates the need to strengthen self-control of patients.

